

ETHOS, PATHOS, LOGOS: THE VERSATILITY OF A HIJAB VIDEO ADVERTISEMENT

**Intan Fitri Aisyah Hamzah,
Naqibah Izzati Mohammad Johan,
Noor Hanim Rahmatⁱ**
Akademi Pengajian Bahasa,
UiTM Shah Alam,
Malaysia

Abstract:

Advertisement is a medium of communication utilized by organizations in order to convey their intended messages to their targeted audience. It can be divided into two main groups which are digital and physical advertising. As for video advertising which is the chosen business document for this paper, it belongs in the former type. Nowadays, it can be seen that more organizations are inclined towards the utilization of video advertising as it is believed as capable in reaching to maximum number of audiences in no time. Therefore, the rhetorical elements of ethos, pathos, and logos are adapted as the instrument in analysing the selected video advertisement. These aforementioned elements are categorized as appeals which serve different functions and have the ability in helping to increase the persuasiveness level. With that, the objective of this paper is to examine how the rhetorical elements are used in the video advertisement of a hijab brand. As for the findings, it shows that ethos, pathos and logos are being used synergically as the persuasive tools to influence the audience. With the presence of this study, it is hoped that it can shed some light on the effectiveness of implementing these rhetorical elements in video advertisements.

Keywords: video advertisement, rhetorical elements, ethos, pathos, logos

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of Study

1.1.1 Business Documents

Business documents are considered as the essentials for any organization of various fields to function effectively. These documents serve the purpose of being the basic foundation which assists employees in working not only systematically but ethically as well. In addition, these documents also act as a tool or platform which is utilized to disseminate information within the organization as externally too. Fundamentally, they can be classified into two different categories which are the formal and informal documents. Memos, emails, and notices are the

ⁱ Correspondence: email intanffitri@gmail.com, naqibahizzati@gmail.com, patanim28@gmail.com

examples for the former type while documents such as annual finance report, project report, press release, business proposals, employee agreement alongside with advertisements belong in the latter type. In this context, advertisements are also regarded as business document as they contain the crucial information regarding the organization. They are embedded with values, beliefs as well as principles that the organization wishes to educate their targeted stakeholders on.

1.1.2 Advertisements

According to Bennet (2010), advertisement is a marketing tool that is integrated with announcements and persuasive messages created by business firms, non-profit organizations, government agencies, and individuals who intend to inform and/or persuade their desired target market or audience on their products, services, organizations or ideas. Fundamentally, advertisement will benefit organizations in many ways as they have the ability to cover wide coverage of local markets. This is due to the fact that, traditional and new media provide a platform to publicize their diverse advertisements endlessly. Other than that, the nature of advertisements of being geographically flexible has also caused many organizations to dynamically produce them in order to educate the consumers on their respective products or services. Corresponding with that, advertisement can be considered as a basic crucial necessity for organizations as it is capable in assisting them to establish and sustain their positions in the ever-changing business environment. Nevertheless, despite having multiple encounters with various advertisements, there are still some people who are not aware with the different types of advertisement. Durmaz (2011) mentioned that advertisement can be categorized into two main types which include digital advertising and physical advertising. For the former type, it includes television advertising, radio advertising, and online advertising. As for the latter type of advertisements, it encompasses of press advertising, mobile billboard advertising, in-store advertising, coffee cup advertising, as well as outdoor (street) advertising.

1.1.3 Video Advertisement

Above all, there is another type of advertisement that has only emerged recently yet managed to be favoured by many organizations already. Kaur, Arumugam and Norimah (2013) suggested that in order to attract more potential customers in the competitive business field, more organizations are resorting to vigorous advertising strategies including video advertisements. It is known as video advertisement and it can be found on multiple social media platforms which include YouTube, Instagram, Facebook and Twitter as well. It can be regarded as a dominant force in the advertising and marketing world due to the significant and effective impacts it carries. One of the main rationales on this worldwide phenomenon is due to the existence of internet and emergence of smartphones. Almost everyone nowadays owns a smartphone regardless their social status as it is now classified as a need specifically on the communication aspect. In addition, more organizations prefer to produce video advertisements as they are aware that everyone has the access to internet. Thus, it will take no time for the audience to discover the video advertisements through their fingertips and then educate as well as entertain themselves with it. Therefore, this paper aims to analyse a specific type of

business document which is the video advertisement and its effectiveness in according to the rhetoric elements.

1.2 Problem Statement

The advancement of technology has created the availability of different types of advertisement to be utilized by organizations to showcase their products and educate their audience about it simultaneously. Philips as cited by Kannan and Hongshuang (2017) stated that organizations have increasingly shift towards the integration of video advertisement as they have come to the realization on the importance of generating a “digital relationship” with their audience. Besides, it can be seen that a lot of researches have done in order to identify the factors which could contribute to the audience’s understanding towards video advertisement yet not much on its persuasiveness.

A study which was conducted by Rodriguez (2017), explored the different types of cues which were considered important by audience in cultivating their comprehension on YouTube advertisements. These cues include music, tone of voice, physical appearance of the actors and the scenery. Regardless, the preference towards cues in video advertisements depends on another external factor which was one’s race or ethnicity. Furthermore, the researcher had only focused on three races or ethnicity which is Hispanic, Latinos as well as Caucasian. Corresponding with that, the researchers believe there is a need to examine whether the aforementioned cues also carry the ability to increase the persuasion level in video advertisement. This is due to the fact that, advertisements are created mainly to persuade the audiences while influencing their purchase intention on the specific product. Thus, this study would provide an insight on the factors which can assist in creating a video advertisement that has a high level of persuasion.

Apart from that, there are a lot of persuasion techniques or appeals available which can be implemented in order to increase the level of persuasion across various medium. One of the most well-known would be the Aristotle’s rhetorical elements which consist of ethos, pathos and logos. Generally, these elements are utilized in political speeches and debates and it has been established to be carrying its own significances. For example, Ko (2015) conducted a study on political persuasion and the adaptation of Aristotelian rhetoric in public policy debate strategies of Taiwan’s President Ma Ying-Jeou. From this study, it is proven that the integration of ethos, pathos, and logos in the debate has made the audience to be influenced and persuaded with the ideas centralized by President Ma. However, there is not much study which analyses the incorporation of rhetorical elements in video advertisements and its effectiveness in persuading the intended audience. Therefore, this study aims to fill in the gap by examining how ethos, pathos and logos are embedded and increase the persuasiveness of a hijab video advertisement.

1.3 Research Objective

The objective of this paper is to examine how the rhetorical elements specifically ethos, pathos and logos are used in the video advertisement for the brand Aidijuma.

1.4 Research Questions

- 1) How is the element of ethos used in video advertisement?
- 2) How is the element of pathos used in video advertisement?
- 3) How is the element of logos used in video advertisement?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Product Advertising

2.1.1 Hijab

It can be seen that recently a lot of international brands are trying to make efforts in incorporating the element of hijab or a hijabi in their advertisements. It is believed that they feel the need to embrace and appreciate the differences in religion as well as culture exists in this world. For example, Nike has come out with their "Pro Hijab" advertisement which emphasizes on women's right to be active without having to worry about their cultural or religion circumstances. Through this advertisement, women are portrayed as capable in conducting various sorts of sports and there is nothing that could prevent them from doing so. As for this study, the researchers have chosen a video advertisement which was produced by a well-known local hijab brand which resonates the same main idea carried by Nike. The video which is entitled as "Aidijuma TVC" on YouTube was produced as a collaborative effort between Aidijuma and Blossom Box Store for TV3's "Clever Girl" broadcast program. The main theme that is highlighted in the video is women empowerment. This is due to the fact that, the video portrays the lifestyle of three young and successful women. They are seen to be navigating different types of vehicles which are a helicopter, a McLaren, and a speed boat with grace in order to make their ways to the usual meet-up place. The integration of these types of vehicles is to serve the purpose of exhibiting women's ability to execute manoeuvres that are usually dominated by men. In a way, this video is trying to educate women that they are capable to be adventurous, energetic, and confident while being shariah compliance at the same time.

2.1.2 Advertisements

Advertisements on the other hand can be spotted almost everywhere nowadays; various billboards are placed along the highways; numerous brand advertisements are posted on social media and also the inclusion of advertisement in traditional media such as the newspaper. As mentioned earlier, advertisements can be divided into two main categories which are digital and physical advertising. Rihan (2010) mentioned that digital advertising requires the use of digital technologies such as the Internet, mobile phones, display advertising and other digital platform. One of the main reasons on the preference towards this type of advertisements is due to the modernization of the world. Millennials are always on the go nowadays and they also want everything to be accessible through their fingertips. Therefore, their worlds revolve around their over-priced smartphones and their faces are fixed towards the screen most of the time. Apart from that, Dayton (2016) suggested that print advertisement is on the verge of becoming a dying or ineffective form of communication between organizations and their intended audience. However, it is still being favoured by the older generation and somehow

this inclination has contributed to the ability of print advertisement to sustain their position in the marketing and business fields. Above all, the researchers believed that both types of advertisements still have its own importance for the organizations and the audience also. Vâlceanu (2011) stated that different types of advertisements have evolved over time and change their nature but they are all still considered as crucial marketing tools for any organizations in introducing their products or services to the audience.

2.1.3 Video Advertisements

There are various types of advertisements and definitely each of it is assigned to specific characteristics or features. Durmaz (2011) defined video advertisement as a type of promotion which utilizes the Internet and World Wide Web for the sole aim of conveying marketing messages in order to attract more customers. Due to its difference in nature, video advertisements carry their own distinct characteristics and one of them is the video duration or length in total. Compared to the television advertisement, this specific type only comes in a relatively short duration ranging from 10 to 30 seconds in total. Pickard as cited by Goodrich, Schiller and Galleta (2011) mentioned that video advertisements are shaped to be made into a shorter duration of time as a way to reduce the consumer annoyance factor and adhere to their tolerance range. In addition, Lai, Lai and Chiang (2015) suggested that as video advertisement comprises the combination of light, colours, sound as well as plotline thus it has become more effective compared to other advertisements. Nevertheless, this type of advertisements is well-received and favoured by many as it is cost-effective compared to being broadcasted through televisions. Organizations could come out with one advertisement, upload it to multiple free video-sharing platforms which include YouTube, Instagram, and Facebook and reach maximum audience in no time.

2.2 Rhetorical Elements

In analysing a business document, several method or instruments such as rhetorical elements, structure or devices can be employed. As for this paper, the foundation for the instrument that was adapted is the Aristotle's rhetorical elements which include ethos, pathos and logos. Generally, this instrument is used in increasing the persuasive level of any documents which could be an advertisement or political speeches. In this context, ethos is defined as an ethical appeal which can be reflected through the quality of the author in being credible as well as trustworthy.

Connors as cited by Ting (2018) indicated that the intelligence, character, and goodwill of an individual are referred to in this type of appeal. In a way, this element highlights on the author's ability to manifest a positive image of himself by appearing to be competent in convincing the audience with his ideas. This research divides Ethos in three different branches namely as credibility, expectation and reference. Credibility discusses about how a brand would communicate their values that describe their brand identity to the audience (Topanno & Topanno, 2014). This element is seen as one of the reasons for a brand to stand out among its competitors in the market. Differentiating its own identity from the others helps the brand to grab the attention of its audience more easily. Another element of ethos is expectation in which Varpio (2018) stated that audience expect authors to deliver their message ethically or

otherwise it would reflect the authors poorly. A brand should not take this matter for granted because once they deliver their message wrongly, it may affect the way audience view their image and automatically will tarnish their reputation. Finally, it is also crucial for a brand to have a good spokesperson to represent their company and at the same time deliver their messages to the audience. In this research, this matter falls under reference. According to Percy and Elliott (2012), persuasive message relies on the 'source' of the message rather than the message itself.

Pathos on the other hand refers to the use of emotional appeal. It will eventually assist to evoke the sense of compassion and also other feelings such as anger, fear, sadness and others within the audience. Demirdogen (2010) suggested that pathos is categorized as a psychological appeal in which it depends on the audience's emotions. In this context, tone of an advertisement is an important element to touch the emotion of the audience. Percy and Elliott (2012) stated that music can represent the tone of an advertisement and helps to evoke and influence consumer's emotion. Furthermore, another element of pathos is 'emphasis'. Brands should emphasize on certain element of their advertisements, so that it can trigger specific reactions in the audience (Varpio, 2018). However, brands also need to be smart in choosing the best emotional reaction that they would like to evoke through their advertisement so that it can influence the audience better. Last but not least, the engagement between a brand and its audience is also a crucial aspect in Pathos. According to Taquini (2016), Pathos highlights the importance of having a proper relationship between the audience and the point of discussion. Meaning that, it is very important for a brand to make sure the audience can make some connection with their brand through the marketing message that they present through the advertisement.

As for logos, it revolves around the rational appeal which emphasizes on logical reasonings. Higgins and Walker (2012) mentioned that this specific characterization is associated with the argument's clarity and integrity rather than the author themselves. Generally, people only acknowledge logos as a type of appeal yet this rhetoric element has its own sub-elements which include clarity, conciseness, and arrangement. Varpio (2018) suggested clarity as an element which does not focus on the logic of the messages carried by the author but also emphasizes on the audiences' ability to comprehend it. In the business industry, advertisement is one of the crucial key factors that are used by organizations to influence and persuade the public in becoming their customers. Therefore, lack of clarity in advertisements produced will not give the maximum effect that every organization yearns for. Balito (2012) on the other hand proposed that conciseness refers to the "straight facts" or "key ideas" which the author would like to present to the audience. Fundamentally, by right each advertisement must be embedded with the main ideas that organizations would like to centralize. This is because: this element would be the "person-in-charge" in communicating the ideas to the audience effectively. In addition, Varpio (2018) indicated that in "arrangement", the disposition of author's ideas must be well-structured in order to ensure that it can be logically conclude by the audience. The inexistence of flow or synchronisation in advertisement can cause major loss to the organizations as it will lead to the audience inability in grasping the messages that they would like to convey.

2.3 Past Researches on Rhetorical Elements

A research was conducted on the use and role of sound design in product advertising (Topanno & Topanno, 2014). This research aims to explore sound design functions in delivering the message of the brand and how it conveys the rhetorical meaning of the advertisement. The study focused on one of the Aristotle Rhetorical Elements which is Ethos since it has capability to evoke the identity and personality of the author and designer of an advertisement. In conducting this study, the researchers used Lancôme's video commercial dated from 1990 to 2010. The advertisement of this beauty product was used to show clearer examples how sound features have been utilized in order to communicate the symbolic meanings of the advertisements. The findings showed that sound design is constructed to match the specific characteristics of every rhetorical element so that it can persuade the audience while watching the advertisement.

Cam (2015) did a study that aimed to see the used of rhetorical structures and the figurative language in magazines' advertisements in Turkey. The study was conducted on 150 automobile advertisements dated from 2012 to the present time and was generated from an auto magazine. Content analysis method was utilized to examine the persuasive elements used in the advertisement. The findings reported that Aristotle Rhetorical Elements were being widely in all of the advertisements. The elements of ethos, pathos and logos were respectively being used as the sources, emotional appeals and logical proofs of the advertisements.

Another research was conducted by Kiholm and Gardemyr (2017) on the strategic use of rhetorical proofs in transformational advertising. Prior to the execution of this research, both of the authors believed that a better comprehension on how transformational advertising can be initiated through the strategic use of the three rhetorical is worth to be conducted. Besides, they also have become aware on the lack of empirical research and no available studies which combine the aforementioned proofs with the theory on transformational advertising. Therefore, the objective of this research was to fill the gap between the theory and practise by analysing the strategic use of rhetoric, specifically on ethos, pathos, logos in order to create a transformational advertisement. In addition, this research employed three different research methods conducted for data collection process which include likelihood of transformational advertising, systematic content analysis and expert interviews through thematic analysis to obtain insights on the strategic use of rhetoric in producing an informational or transformational advertisement. Above all, this research has found out that the incorporation of logos whether directly or indirectly did help to induce effective communication through the advertisements.

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Research Design

This research will be implementing a qualitative method research design. According to Yamagata-Lynch, Skutnik, Garty and Do (2016), qualitative research is used with the aim to have a better understanding of the interactions that happen in human activity. Not only that, Rizka (2016) stated that qualitative research should be used for a research to understand a phenomenon better especially if the research would like to analyse the speech, utterance,

written text and context of a particular data like advertisement. Therefore, based on the criteria of the past studies, this research uses a qualitative method since it will be analysing a persuasive technique used by an advertisement by Aidijuma. Aristotle Rhetorical Element will be used as the main technique to analyse the advertisement. This research also uses qualitative method because it will be analysing one document only which is in line with the document analysis procedure. According to Bowen (2017) document analysis is a systematic procedure to review and evaluate any printed or electronic document.

3.2 Sample

This research uses purposive sampling to choose the product advertisement. According to Sarstedt, Shaltoni, Bengart and Lehmann (2017), purposive sampling involves the judgement of the researchers in selecting sample whereby the researchers can include or choose any data that they find the most appropriate for the study. In this paper, the advertisement is chosen based on several qualities that the researchers find would help them to get a rich data. The first element is whether the advertisement possesses the Aristotle rhetorical elements that need to be analysed in the study. Besides, the advertisement also should not exceed more than one-minute duration because it will be too lengthy to be analysed. Based on the agreed criteria, purposive sampling is chosen in order to guide the researchers to find the most suitable video advertisement on YouTube.

3.3 Instrument

3.3.1 Template of Instrument

Table 1: Template for summary of findings

Rhetorical/ Linguistic Category	Characteristics	Evidence from Document	Explanation
Ethos	(i) Credibility: Values communicated to the audience. Each brand selects a set of values that constitute the core of the brand identity and are fundamental to increase the company recognition (brand identity), to differentiate the company and its offerings from those of competitors (Toppano & Toppano, 2014).		
	(ii) Expectation: Audience expect authors to deliver their message ethically or otherwise it would reflect the authors poorly (Varpio, 2018).		
	(iii) Reference: Source In Ethos, the persuasive message relies on the 'source' of the message rather than the message itself (Percy & Elliott, 2012).		
Pathos	(i) Tone: Music can represent the tone of the advertisement and helps to evoke and influence consumer's emotion (Percy & Elliott, 2012).		
	(ii) Emphasis:		

	The author emphasizes certain element in the advertisement to trigger specific reactions in the writing (Varpio, 2018).		
	(iii) Engagement: Relationship Pathos highlights the importance of having a proper relationship between the audience and the point of discussion (Taquini, 2016).		
Logos:	(i) Clarity: Element which does not focus on the logic of the messages carried by the author but also emphasizes on the audiences' ability to comprehend it (Varpio, 2018).		
	(ii) Conciseness: Refers to the "straight facts" or "key ideas" which the author would like to present to the audience (Bolatito, 2012).		
	(iii) Arrangement: The disposition of author's ideas must be well-structured in order to ensure that it can be logically conclude by the audience (Varpio, 2018).		

3.3.2 Instrument

Table 1 is used as the main instrument that helps the researchers to analyse the advertisement. The table is divided into four columns which are the Rhetorical or Linguistics Category, characteristics, evidence from document and explanation. The first two columns are used to categorize the Aristotle Rhetorical Elements and the three characteristics of each element. The fourth column will be used to record the evidence from the video by providing brief description of every scene together with the duration of each scene. Finally, the last column provides a section that is specifically designed for the researchers to provide explanation about the evidences that have been found from the advertisement. This template is used to guide the researchers in reporting the findings of the study in the next chapter.

3.4 Data Collection

The researchers surf the internet specifically the YouTube to find the most suitable video to be analysed. Several advertisements from different brands are listed and viewed together before choosing the best option. The advertisement that is being chosen is taken due to the clear representation of the use of Aristotle Rhetorical Elements.

3.5 Data Analysis

To analyse the data that have been collected, the research used Aristotle Rhetorical Elements as the base of the analysis. The video advertisement is analysed thoroughly and every scene which has any element that is connected to the Aristotle Rhetorical Element is recorded. The researchers categorize them into separate group which are ethos, pathos and logos. In making sure that the analysis is reliable, various past studies are referred to.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

As being mentioned in the earlier chapters, this study analyses the use of rhetorical elements of ethos, pathos and logos in a video advertisement. According to Varpio (2018), ethos is typically associated with the trustworthiness and credibility of the writer. Pathos meanwhile is related to the emotion of the audience and how persuasive message affects their feelings (Higgin & Walker, 2012). Finally, logos are linked with rational appeal to the audience whereby logical reasoning, evidence and appropriate data are provided to the audience in order to influence them (Ting, 2018).

4.2 Ethos in Video Advertisement

In the video advertisement, all three characteristics of Ethos are being used. Firstly, the credibility of the brand can be clearly seen throughout the video with the incorporation of three different vehicles which are accompanied by three different slogans which explain the scenes. The portrayal of the scenes highlights the image of the brand as a leading hijab line which celebrates women from various backgrounds. The advertisement also successfully shows the versatility of the brand which definitely is one of its main values. This can be seen through the whole advertisement whereby it avoids the use of the portrayal of a typical woman which usually shows the feminine side of a woman. This brand however instills the unsung sides of a woman by showing the three women handle three different vehicles that are associated with the man. By portraying the diverse sides of women, this brand shows that it wants to offer something new and different to the customers.

While Ethos also plays with the expectation of the audience as their persuasive tool, this advertisement attracts the attention of the audience by putting some twists in its plotline. Rather than focusing on the femininity of the woman, this advertisement portrays the unexplored sides of the women. This can be seen when all of the woman characters in the advertisement are portrayed differently although they are all going to the same direction. This shows how this brand would like to celebrate women without looking at their backgrounds and status. This definitely surpasses the expectation of the audience because this advertisement has ironically showed how hijab who supposedly cover their head has opened them to more opportunities and things to be explored without putting them with any limitation.

Finally, just like any other advertisements, this advertisement also presents its own spoke person or the main face of its product at the ending scenes of the video. Using its own founder as the spokesperson of the brand helps the audience to remember about their product. This is because, the founder of this product is a well-known celebrity and she also originates her own name in her brand. Therefore, people would easily recall the brand's name and will not be confused with the other similar product of different brands in the market.

4.3 Pathos in Video Advertisement

The element of Pathos is being used widely throughout the video. Firstly, it can be seen through the use of background music of the advertisement. The soft background music helps to naturalise the strong narratives of the three-women characters and the depiction of each scene

in the advertisement. This arouses the curiosity of the audience on the advertisement because the choice of melodious song in the advertisement is contradict with the activities which the three women go through in the advertisement.

Besides, the brand attracts the emotion of the audience by showing the relevancy of their product to the target audience. The advertisement uses the simple portrayal of the three women to emphasize how their product will be relevant despite the background of the users. This can be seen in all three scenes of the women who manage to control three different vehicles that are used for different means. All of these scenes show the versatility of the brand itself who are used in three different situations while at the same time putting the emphasis on how its products is relevant to be used in a completely different environment. By doing so, the brand indirectly would like to convey a message on how the brand celebrates women despite the differences in their backgrounds. This is a great move in order to make sure that their target audience will not feel left out and realize that their existence is being celebrated by the brand. Not only that, it will also help to make women out there to feel that they are as powerful as the women portrayed in the advertisement.

Lastly, this advertisement also can be seen to touch the emotion of the audience by establishing a relationship with the audience through the way they highlight the theme of their brand. The chosen theme which is women empowerment helps their target audience to feel a sense of belonging with the brand and indirectly engage them with the products. Rather than just showing women in their natural settings, a more 'challenging' sides of women are shown. This can be seen from the way they pair the women with the vehicles that are usually will be associated with the man. By doing this, it helps the female audience to engage more with the advertisement since it indirectly evokes a powerful emotion in them.

4.4 Logos in the advertisement

Logos is also used in the advertisement. The clarity of the intended message in the advertisement can be seen and comprehend easily by the audience. The use of the vehicles to symbolise the real-world situations definitely help to deliver the message in details. The incorporation of different types of vehicles in the video is actually implying the ability of women to handle different type of situations in real life. The vehicles are used as a symbol or representation of reality which definitely is full of ups and downs. Therefore, by wearing this scarf, all women will be capable to handle all situations with ease.

Furthermore, the details of the advertisement are clearly depicted to the audience especially when the advertisement pairs the scenes with different key items to explain the features and characteristics of the product. Throughout the whole video, the author is trying to create correlations between the specific features of the scarf (key points) with the acts done by the women. For example, at 0.06 the second woman is seen to be driving a sport car which is fundamentally known to be super-fast. At the same time, the first key point is inserted in the shot and the wordings used reflect the act done by the woman. From here, it can be deduced that the author is trying to convince the audience that their product which is the scarf can withstand acceleration and will stay in shape no matter what while being graceful. As for the second key point which is "Menongkah Arus", it is linked with the act of handling a water transportation. Here, the author is trying to imply that by wearing their scarf, all women is

capable in handling all situations because the phrase “menongkah arus” can be used in different context and does not carry the literal meaning which is handling waves. This is due to the fact that, in Bahasa Melayu “menongkah arus” could be used in “menongkah arus pemodenan” as well. Last but not least, the key point “elegan sepanjang zaman” is associated with the first woman as she walks at the hangar elegantly.

Finally, the element of logos can be seen from the well-structured storyline that is portrayed in the advertisement. The scene in the video is arranged systematically in order to help the audience follow the intended message until the end of the advertisement. The sequence of the women’s entrances in the video has been properly done. This is due to the fact that, these women are introduced to the audience one by one which projects well-structured idea. Besides, throughout the video these women take turns to be in the shot after they have made their first appearance which creates the elements of cohesion and coherence in the video. By doing this, it has helped the audience to understand the underlying plotline.

4.5 Summary of Ethos, Pathos, and Logos

Based on the findings that have been reported from the previous chapter, the element of ethos is used widely in the advertisement. This element is mandatory for every advertisement because it helps to build a good image of the brand. Not only that, for an advertisement to be swiftly popular, it is compulsory for the brand to invest some money and endorse a spoke person.

It is crucial for advertisement to influence the emotion of the audience. This is because; it is usually the catalyst that helps them in making decision to choose a certain product. Pathos is the element that should be used in order to appeal to the emotion of the audience. While there are a lot of emotions that advertisers can choose to instil in their audience, it is important for them to carefully considering the best emotion to be used so that their message can be delivered successfully.

All in all, logos are the type of appeal which can be considered as the crucial ones. This is due to the fact that, it revolves around the logical aspect of the key ideas. A lack of this specific appeal will only reflect the organization’s failure to centralize legit message intended towards their audience. In return, it can cause the audience to build a perception that these organizations are not reliable and will decrease their loyalty towards them.

4.6 Discussions

4.6.1 Ethos

Based on the study that have been made, it can be seen that this advertisement clearly portrays its credibility as an elegant brand by delivering its value to the audience through the use of narratives between three women who are portrayed differently compared to the usual and natural settings of a woman. By doing this, the audience get to grab the idea that brand is implementing that they have their own class and standard. This is aligned with a study by Topanno & Topanno (2014) which analyse a Lancôme advertisement. In the advertisement, the female character is depicted as someone is very sophisticated in order to help the brand to communicate their values to the audience as a leading beauty company.

Ethos is also usually associated with how brands persuade their audience by using a spoke person or their representatives. This advertisement also can be seen uses the same strategy to persuade their audience. However, while other brands usually will appoint a famous celebrity to represent their brands, this brand makes full use of its own founder to represent her own brand. Since she is someone who is well known for being very elegant and feminine, it definitely goes well with their brand, thus help them to build a good image in the eyes of the public. Just like killing two birds with one stone, by appointing its own founder as the spoke person of the brand, she will not only help to influence the audience with her personality but also her expertise on her own brand. This is crucial and can be seen to be in accordance with a study by Cam (2015) which stated that how source of a message (ethos) should be an expert and is knowledgeable about the brand in order to communicate the brand's message successfully.

4.6.2 Pathos

Pathos is usually associated as the main factor that plays with the emotion of the audience. Based on the advertisement, every element of pathos is being fully utilised to gain a good reaction from the audience. The background music that accompanies the advertisement truly compliments the storyline and helps to hold the attention of the audience. The same evidence can be seen from the study from Kiholm and Gårdemyr (2017) which highlights the importance of music in an advertisement because it can provide fruitful effects and touch the emotion of the audience positively.

4.6.3 Logos

Based on the advertisement, it is evident that the three main subcomponents of logos which are clarity, conciseness, and arrangement are apparent in this video advertisement. The integration of these elements has facilitated to increase the effectiveness level of the video. This is because: the characteristic of "clarity" is responsible in enhancing the audience's overall understanding on the video's centralized main ideas. Meanwhile, "conciseness" has guided the audience to comprehend the correlations between the specific features of the scarf with the acts done by the women. Lastly, "arrangement" has created a flow to be followed by the audience as well as the elements of cohesion and coherence. This finding on the effectiveness of incorporating logos and its subcomponents is consistent with the study conducted by Kiholm and Gardemyr (2017) on the strategic use of rhetorical proofs in transformational advertising.

5. Recommendations & Suggestions

5.1 Recommendations

While analysing this advertisement, one of the things that can be pointed out is that advertisers should be bolder in depicting fresh portrayal of their brands to the audience. This will help their product to stand out among the similar products that are being promoted in the market. Providing the audience with an outstanding advertisement will definitely attract their attentions and give a good image of the brand itself. However, just like what Aidijuma did in their advertisement, future brands which plan to come out with an advertisement should make

sure that they are not only being creative with their advertisement but also successfully delivering and communicating their message and values to the audience. Therefore, producing an advertisement should not be something that is taken for granted but needed thorough planning by the brand itself.

Based on the findings and conclusions made for this study, it is also highly recommended for organization to always incorporate the rhetorical elements in their business documents especially the video advertisements. By integrating ethos, pathos, and logos in it, organizations will be receiving indirect guide in generating a high-quality video advertisement which is embedded with legit underlying theme and meaning. Not just that, it will definitely help to increase the persuasiveness level of their documents ultimately. It is crucial for these organizations to actually put on a lot of effort in this aspect as it is one of the methods for them to present themselves to the audience. Besides, consistent quality content produced by an organization carries the ability to enhance and sustain brand loyalty within the audience. Therefore, if any organization regarded this platform as not important then they should expect less audience engagement over time.

5.2 Suggestions

Since this research is only being done in a short period of time, many areas cannot be analysed thoroughly. For the future research, more studies should be done on this topic by using a more detailed method. Rather than only focusing on one data collection method, a mixed method can be done to measure the effectiveness of the advertisements on the eyes of the audience. By doing so, the study will be more reliable and informative since the data are not only analyse through the advertisement but it also takes the opinion of the audience into account.

This current study only employs a single instrument in analysing this specific type of business document (video advertisement) which is through the use of rhetoric elements: ethos, pathos, and, logos. Therefore, it is advisable for the future researchers to expand this study by incorporating another instrument in investigating the effectiveness of video advertisement. For example, researchers can add on rhetorical devices which include the use of linguistic aspects such as simile, metaphor, hyperbole and others. By opting to this methodology, it can help the researchers to obtain a rich and stable data which eventually will provide them with more insights on the specific topic of interest. With that, a more holistic conclusion can be drawn from the future research.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the advertisement that is analyzed in this study can be seen to use all aspects of Aristotle Rhetorical Elements which are Ethos, Pathos and Logos. The element of Ethos can be seen to be used in the way the brand conveys its values and messages to the audience. Meanwhile, Pathos is used in order to evoke the emotion of the audience by the way the brand highlights the theme of its advertisement. Last but not least, Logos can be detected through the implementation of clear arrangement of storyline throughout the advertisement. The incorporation of these elements definitely has increased the persuasiveness of the advertisement as a whole.

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About the Author(s)

Intan Fitri Aisyah Hamzah and Naqibah Izzati Mohammad Johan are taking Master of Language Studies in Universiti Teknologi Mara (UiTM), Shah Alam, Selangor. They are currently in their first semester of their study. They are very much interested in linguistics research areas such as Sociolinguistics and Discourse Analysis.

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